

FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: the theory of physical education and its practice are always in development and perfected. The results of the practice, scientific research data, enrich the theory and methodology of physical education with new principles and laws. Therefore, the subject of the theory and methodology of physical education cannot consist of fixed information. The theory and methodology of physical education relies on the achievements of Social, natural, Pedagogical Sciences.

Keywords: physical education, theory, methodology, research, qualification, movement, knowledge, practice, result, skill

The science of the theory and methodology of physical education as a subject of study focused on the specialty teaches the fundamental system of knowledge, human physical perfection and the General Laws of achievement and management for physical education specialists. The theory of physical education interprets and summarizes the existing facts about physical education in the way of scientific science. As an applied science, it provides practical, theoretical knowledge of the means of physical perfection of a person, forms of physical education and his methodology, increases the reserve of vital-necessary skills and skills of character.

The theory of physical education and its practice are always in development and perfected. The results of the practice, scientific research data, enrich the theory and methodology of physical education with new principles and laws. Therefore, the subject of the theory and methodology of physical education cannot consist of fixed information. The theory and methodology of physical education relies on the achievements of Social, natural, Pedagogical Sciences. The theory and methodology of physical education in any case uses the most general laws, principles and rules that analyze the basis of scientific pedagogy, including for all sports disciplines, these laws, principles and rules are appropriate and have a specific meaning.

The formation as an academic discipline and its development were caused by the emergence and aspiration of the theoretical idea that it is possible to increase the physical fitness of members of society. With this, the rule and laws that it is possible to control the physical development of a person proved to be of high effect in social labor and military practice. The content of the theory and methodology of physical education includes those below:

- the fact that physical education is special to society, is associated with other forms of education as a social worker;
- the purpose of physical education, its general tasks and principles;
- means of physical education, methodological principles;

- training in character, teaching methods;
- development of physical qualities;
- exercise and its structure of the uqitshp process;
- forms of Organization of exercise training;
- planning the physical education process and its report;
- features of the methodology of physical education;
- physical education of children of preschool age and school age;
- description of the process of sports training.

The General Laws of physical education in the form of a pedagogical process are the subject of study of the theory of physical education. General laws are understood as the private aspects of the physical education of qualified athletes, those who have just begun to practice physical activities, including any class of the population: children, adolescents, young people, middle-aged people, adults and the elderly. In addition, the methodology of Physical Education also defines some of the private laws of physical education as the subject of study, and in the implementation of the General Laws of the pedagogical process, the methods of "general and professional special physical training", "methodology of sports training" are clearly used. Within each of these styles, there is their own private style.

The diversity of styles is determined by which Psychological Types of those involved belong to, their age, gender, what occupation they are, and the chosen sports specialty (methodology of physical education of children of school age, methodology of physical education of women, etc.k.)to be specific and appropriate. The methodology of some disciplines of sports pedagogy (methods of teaching sports games, gymnastics, etc.) is formed in a separate independently separated way of scientific and educational disciplines. And the science of the theory and methodology of physical education forms them with single theoretical and methodological foundations, complements its rules as a science in the system of Pedagogical Sciences by the nature of the subjects of study at the expense of Social, Psychological and biological factors.

Sources of physical education theory

For the development of the theory and methodology of physical education, the next are the main sources:

- ways to raise Physical Culture and sports in our country, and the current situation, about the decisions, laws of humiliation;
- progressive teachings about the comprehensive maturation of a person during the development of his society. These teachings consist not only in making a sound for the comprehensive development of a person, but also in trying to unravel its content, as well as theoretically, practically substantiating the ways of implementing these ideas;
- a system of theoretical, practical knowledge accumulated by scientific research and other mixed Sciences on physical education, carried out and carried out in the field of theory and methodology of physical education;
- experience of the life practice of a social lifestyle, the demand of society for people with high physical fitness;
- the knowledge of the connotations of physical education of members of society and, on this basis, the emergence of a desire to structure and control the system of human physical maturation;

- concepts of Physical Culture, in which the system of physical education is considered a branch of the spirituality of an existing society;

- physical education practice-as a resource, it examines the viability of theoretical rules, uses original ideas born in practice, and they enrich the theory and methodology of Education.

- archival materials, personal observation results (Diaries, plans of athletes and their coaches, competition statements, synopsis, lecture texts.) enrich the theory of physical education and serve as a source for it .

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